

"Evaluating the Effect of Perceived Social Support on Self-Care Behavior of Patients with Heart Failure: A Randomized Clinical Trial"

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Abstract

Lack of Social Support (SS) in patients with Heart Failure (HF) may be a barrier to performing daily activities, especially in older patients. Elderly patients with HF are likely to live alone and therefore, the relationship between their daily living conditions and their Self-Care behaviors is indirectly associated with perceived SS. Perceived SS is the strongest predictor of Self-Care behavior in HF patients.

Aim: The present study was to evaluate the effect of a dual nursing intervention, with an educational approach at the discharge of patients with HF and subsequently, structured telephone follow-up, on perceived SS and its effect on Self-Care behavior, for a period of 12 months after the patients' discharge from the hospital, in relation to usual care.

Material - Method: This is a Randomized Clinical Trial (RCT), with an intervention and control group, which was carried out at the Cardiology Clinic of the Secondary General Hospital of Serres. 186 hospitalized patients with HF (NYHA I-IV), who met the admission criteria and were scheduled for discharge, were randomized. The individuals randomized to the intervention group (N=93) received a personalized educational approach, with one education session and the provision of an information leaflet, before discharge from the hospital and subsequently, telephone follow-up and support for a period of 12 months. Data were collected

in five time periods, the first at discharge and followed by four post-experimental measurements over the course of one year, at the 1st week, at the 1st and 6th months and at 12 months. The control group (N=93) did not receive any intervention, beyond usual care. The assessment of perceived SS was carried out using the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), while the assessment of Self-Care Behavior was carried out using the European Heart Failure Self-Care Behavior Scale - 9 item (EHFScBS-9). For the statistical analysis of the data, for the studied parameters, the average level per time period was studied, with the effect size, difference, and Cohen's d coefficient. The change in the Self-Care scale, over the follow-up time, was tested using Linear Mixed Models (linearmixedmodels), from which the Dependence Coefficients (β) and their Standard Errors (standarderrors=SE) were obtained. The interaction between time and intervention was also tested. The investigation of the association of demographic characteristics with the level of Self-Care was carried out using Multiple Linear Regression. The correlations between the scales, Gr9-EHFScBS and MSPSS to test the relationship, were carried out using the Pearson linear correlation coefficient (r). The statistical significance level was set at 0.05. The internal validity test for the data collected with the MSPSS and Gr9-EHFScBS scales was carried out using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The statistical program SPSS-26.0 was used for the statistical analysis.

Results: Of the N=186 randomized patients, 40.9% (38 patients) of the intervention group and 31.2% (29 patients) of the control group completed the study. The mean age of the patients was 79.2 (SD=8.6). The change in score on the total self-care behavior scale showed an improvement for the intervention group (b=-0.85, p=0.05). The correlation of total self-care behavior with total perceived SS was found to be negative (p<0.001). From the Regression Analysis, for the effect of clinicodemographic characteristics, on the level of overall self-care behavior, it was found that the perceived SS from Family/Significant Others (SO) was found to be statistically significantly correlated with the level of Self-Care behavior (b=-0.27, p=0.002), where higher perceived SS from Family/SO was associated with better self-care behavior.

Conclusions: The findings of this study revealed that the effect of the dual nursing intervention on the Self-Care behavior of patients with HF was found to be enhanced by the nursing educational approach, nursing follow-up and perceived support, empowerment, and increased patient awareness, leading to better management of the chronic and clinically evolving syndrome.

Keywords: Heart Failure, Nursing Intervention, Self-Care Behavior, Self-efficacy, Social Support

Introduction

Perceived SS is one of the psychosocial factors, a belief that help, support, attention and care are available from others (Family/SO, Friends) and it has been found that the support they have received is more valuable for their health outcomes (Gene et al., 2013; Shahriari et al., 2016; Chamberlain, 2017). Perceived SS, as a widely used concept, refers to any intervention process through which social relationships can promote health, well-being and prosperity, and refers to the social resources that individuals perceive to have or that are actually provided to them by non-professional caregivers, by voluntary support groups, but also by informal support (Family/SO, Friends, neighbors, relatives) (Gronwold et al., 2021). Lack of self-efficacy in chronic HF patients may be a barrier to performing daily activities, especially in older patients (De Vecchis et al., 2017; Buck et al., 2018). Research shows that elderly HF patients are particularly likely to live alone and therefore, the relationship of their daily living conditions with their Self-Care behaviors is indirectly associated with perceived self-efficacy (Weissman & Russell, 2018; Irani et al., 2019). According to the research of Jo et al., (2020), overall perceived self-efficacy had a significant impact on the Self-Care behaviors of chronic patients. Specifically, the results of the research showed that perceived self-efficacy was the strongest predictor of Self-Care behavior in HF patients.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of a dual nursing intervention, with an educational approach at the discharge of patients with HF and subsequently, structured telephone follow-up, on perceived SS and its effect on Self-Care behavior, for a period of 12 months after the patients' discharge from the hospital, in relation to usual care.

Materials and methods

Study population

The study population consisted of all patients with HF who were hospitalized at the Cardiology Clinic of the Secondary General Hospital of Serres and were scheduled for discharge. The entry of the first patient with HF into the study and with scheduled discharge took place in April 2019, while the last patient with HF who participated in the study was in August of the same year. This was followed by telephone contact with the above patients, which took place in 4 time periods, the 1st week, the 1st and 6th months and at 12 months, after the patients' discharge from the hospital. The study was completed in August 2020, with the recording of the last annual telephone contact of the last patient, upon entry into the study.

Criteria for inclusion of patients in the study were as follows: • Patients with a documented diagnosis of HF, regardless of NYHA functional classification, • Patients aged ≥ 18 years, • Patients with HF confirmed by a cardiologist, according to the criteria of the ESC, with confirmed positive echocardiographic criteria for the structure and function of the heart, •

Patients with HF who knew how to write, read and understand the Greek language. **The exclusion criteria were as follows:** Patients with active myocardial ischemia, • Patients with congenital heart disease, • Patients with planned major surgery within six months, • Patients with recent heart surgery (coronary artery angioplasty, coronary artery bypass grafting, valve replacement - valvuloplasty), • Patients who suffered from active cancer, • Patients who lived in an institution, • Patients who did not understand or speak the Greek language, • Patients with a history of psychiatric disorder, • Patients with CKD on dialysis/hemodialysis, • Patients for whom telephone contact was not possible due to lack of infrastructure, • Patients who were not informed that they suffered from HF, as well as patients with HF, who refused to participate in the study and did not sign the informed consent form, • Patients with concomitant musculoskeletal disease, which affects physical activity.

Sample size calculation

The sample size was calculated using the power analysis method using the statistical program G*Power version 3.1.9.2 (Faul et al., 2007).

Randomization

After informing and consenting to participate in the study, patients with HF were randomly assigned to two groups, the intervention and control groups. To create the random allocation of patients to each group, randomization was implemented with Matlab software, using the randperm function, which is used to distribute (permutation) numbers into groups (classes). Patients who agreed to participate in the study were assigned a number, starting from 1 to 186, according to the order in which they were approached. The patients, who had given written consent to participate in the study, did not know which of the two groups they belonged to, except for the researcher and she after opening the numbered, opaque and sealed randomization envelopes. With this method of randomization, the researcher was unbiased in terms of the allocation of patients to the two groups, intervention and control.

Ethical considerations

The research was conducted at the Cardiology Clinic of the General Hospital of Serres. Written, informed consent for participation was obtained from all patients, after an explanation of the purpose and procedure of the study. Participation was voluntary and anonymity was maintained. In addition, all participants were informed of their rights to refuse or discontinue participation, in accordance with the ethical standards of the 1983 Declaration of Helsinki.

Measurement Tools

The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) was used to assess SS. The scale consists of 12 items, which are rated on a Likert-type scale. Responses range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). The 12 items tend to be divided into three subgroups of factors, which are related to the source of SS, Family (FAM), Friends (FRIENDS) or Significant Others (SO) (Zimet et al., 1988). The scale assesses and evaluates the perceived SS from family, friends, but also some significant others, who are close to them and offer them support and empowerment (Wenn et al., 2022). The values of the subfactors are calculated from the sum of the scores, which results from the four items of each group. The total score of the questionnaire is calculated from the sum of the scores, which results from all the subfactors. The lowest value from the subscales is 4 and the highest is 28, while from the entire scale (total value), the lowest value is 12 and the highest is 84. Higher scores reflect more perceived SS (Zimet et al., 1988; Khaledi et al., 2014). The MSPSS questionnaire has been shown to be valid and reliable, with adequate measurements of the perceived SS scale in patients with HF. It was found to have good to excellent internal consistency and test-retest reliability during weighing (Wenn et al., 2022).

To assess Self-Care behavior, either overall or one of its dimensions, the easy-to-use scale The European Heart Failure Self-Care Behavior Scale was used, which can be completed by the patients themselves in a short period of time. This tool concerns Self-Care behavior, with a focus mainly on self-preservation-self-maintenance and which scale was created in 2003 by Dutch and Swedish researchers (Jaarsma et al., 2009). The tool assesses Self-Care behaviors related to the disease of HF. The EHFScBS scale is used to examine three different theoretical aspects, different approaches to self-care behavior, self-service behaviors, medication compliance, seeking help at the right time and adopting Self-Care behaviors, as well as adapting activities. The questionnaire is easy to complete and requires very little time to complete, and the Cronbach's alpha for the whole was found to be 0.81 (Jaarsma et al., 2003; Jaarsma et al., 2013). The questionnaire was originally twelve items, but was later revised to nine items, EHFScBS-9. The revised version of the tool, which is used in the present study, consists of nine questions, with answers on a five-point Likert-type scale, from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). It has been weighted in the Greek Cypriot population with HF for the Greek version. The total score is calculated from the cumulative score for each item and ranges from 9 to 45, with higher scores indicating poorer Self-Care behaviors. The questionnaire has been found to measure change in behavior over time. The reliability and validity of the Greek version of the tool, Gr9- EHFScBS, has been tested using Cronbach's alpha and obtained a value of $\alpha=0.73$ for overall self-care (Lambrinou et al., 2014).

Procedure

Participants were selected during their hospitalization in the hospital, before discharge. An important role in the sample selection process was played by the medical and nursing staff of the Hospital's Cardiology Clinic, by providing information to the researcher regarding the clinical condition of the discharged patients (presence of comorbidities, EF, echocardiographic evidence of cardiac dysfunction). The researcher was informed about the planned discharges of stabilized patients, the time period before their discharge, at the time of preparation of the patient's informational note, by their treating physician. The researcher then studied the medical file of each patient and the nursing staff provided data from the clinic's Patient Registry on readmissions, the total number of days of hospitalization of the patients, as well as on the patients' supportive environment. The necessary information regarding echocardiographic evidence of cardiac dysfunction, HF, the presence of comorbidities and medication was provided to the researcher by the medical staff. Subsequently, after the researcher had studied the medical file of each prospective participating patient for the existence of documented diagnosed HF and provided that the specific patients met the eligibility criteria for entry into the study, the researcher approached the patients, explaining the conduct of the specific study, its purpose and objectives. This was followed by the randomization of the patients into the intervention group and the control group. The patients who agreed to take part in the study were assigned a number, starting from 1 to 186, according to the order in which they were approached. The patients, who had given written consent to participate in the study, did not know which of the two groups they belonged to, except for the researcher and her after opening the numbered, opaque and sealed randomization envelopes. Data collection was carried out in two phases. The first phase concerned the patient's inclusion in the study (pre-measurement) and the second concerned the post-measurement, upon completion of the program at one year (1st week, 1st and 6th month and at one year). In the first phase (pre-measurement), the scale was completed by all patients who participated in the study, on the day of discharge, before the educational intervention. The completion was carried out by the patients themselves, in the presence of the researcher, who, in case of clarifications from the patient, intervened to help him. In case of weakness of the patient, due to problems, inability to read, reduced vision, severe heart failure, the completion was done by the researcher, through an interview. Also, on the day of discharge, all patients in the study were given to complete the special form recording the clinicodemographic characteristics. The collection of clinical and demographic data provided particular assistance to the researcher, during telephone communication with the patients. The clinical characteristics helped in the evaluation of the clinical condition of the patients, as they provided information on the existence of possible comorbidities. Also, the completion of demographic data, helped the researcher during the telephone interview and follow-up of the patients, in providing an individualized nursing educational approach. At the

same time, with the delivery of the questionnaires and the recording forms, all patients were given the special educational printed material for the HF to be studied and subsequently, the patients in the intervention group took part in the educational process by the researcher. In the second phase, after discharge from the hospital, the data collection was carried out, through a telephone interview, by the researcher, where all patients were re-evaluated in terms of perceived SS and self-care behaviors, in the 1st week, in the 1st and 6th months, as well as in the 1st year, after the first recording and evaluation at their entry into the study (post-experimental measurements). Each patient, upon discharge from the hospital, received a package containing:

- the special informational printed material for HF to be studied, entitled: "Learning to Live Embracing Heart Failure",
- the printed material for Recording Telephone Communication Data.

Statistical Analysis

The missing values in the statements of the MSPSS, EHFS_cBS-9 scales were replaced using Multiple Imputation. The distributions of the quantitative variables were checked for normality of their distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov criterion. For those that were normally distributed, the mean and standard deviations (SD) were used to describe them, while for those that were not normally distributed, the median and interquartile range were also used. Absolute (N) and relative (%) frequencies and percentages were used to describe the qualitative variables (categorical variables, gender, marital status, comorbidities, educational level, etc.). For quantitative variables, they were used and presented as Mean - Mean Level and Standard Deviation (SD). For the comparison of proportions, the Pearson's χ^2 test (Pearson Chi-Square test) was used. The correlations between the MSPSS and EHFS_cBS-9 scales, to test the relationship, were done using the Pearson linear correlation coefficient (r). The effect size of the intervention, the Mean Level of perceived SS and Self-Care behavior, per time period, was studied, with the difference size, the Cohen's d coefficient. The change in the Self-Care behavior scale, at the follow-up time, was tested using Linear Mixed Models (linearmixedmodels), from which the Dependence Coefficients (β) and their Standard Errors (standarderrors=SE) were obtained. The interaction between time and intervention was also tested. The possible moderating role of clinicodemographic characteristics, the investigation of the moderating factors in the relationship between perceived SS and Self-Care behavior, was done using Linear Regression and interaction coefficients. The reliability of the MSPSS, EHFS_cBS-9 scales, was studied using the internal consistency coefficient, Cronbach's alpha. The significance levels are two-sided and the statistical significance was set at 0.05. The SPSS 26.0 statistical program was used for the analysis.

Study Results

Sample Description

Table 1. Number of Patients in the Study

	<i>Group</i>		
	<i>Intervention</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Total</i>
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
			186
<i>Discharge</i>	93 (100)	93 (100)	(100)
			166
<i>One Week</i>	85 (91,4)	81 (87,1)	(89,2)
			162
<i>One Month</i>	84 (90,3)	78 (83,9)	(87,1)
			156
<i>Six Months</i>	81 (87,1)	75 (80,6)	(83,9)
<i>One Year</i>	38 (40,9)	29 (31,2)	67 (36)

As can be seen from the above table 1., the sample consisted of 186 patients, of whom 93 (50%) belonged to the intervention group and 93 (50%) to the control group. Over time, the number of participants in both groups changed, due to non-contact or patient deaths. Specifically, 36.6% of patients (34 patients) died in the intervention group and 49.5% (46 patients) in the control group.

Unreachable Contact

The following table presents the number of study patients who did not respond to the researcher's telephone calls during the corresponding time periods of the nursing telephone follow-up.

Table 2. Frequency of Unreachable Contact

	Discharge	One Week	One Month	Six Months	One Year
<i>Intervention</i>					
Did not answer	-	-	-	-	21 (22.6%)

Control				
Did not answer	-	-	-	18 (19.4%)
Total				
Did not answer	-	-	-	39 (20.9%)

From the above table 2 it is observed that all patients up to 6 months answered the phone calls, in the corresponding time periods. However, in the 1st year, it was not possible to communicate with 22.6% (21 patients), of the intervention group and with 19.4% (18 patients), of the control group,

Demographic Characteristics by Group

Table 3. Demographic Characteristics by Group

		Intervention Group, N = 93	Control Group, N = 93	P- value
		N (%)	N (%)	
Sex				
	Male	52 (55,9)	49 (52,7)	0,768÷
	Female	41 (44,1)	44 (47,3)	
Age		79,9 (8,4)	78,5 (8,8)	0,363+
Educational level				
	Compulsory Education	83 (89,2)	77 (82,8)	0,439÷
	Secondary Education	9 (9,7)	14 (15,1)	
	Higher/Higher Education	1 (1,1)	2 (2,2)	
Family Status				
	Married	62 (67)	52 (56)	0,175÷
	Single (Widower, Divorced, Never Married)	31 (33)	41 (44)	
Professional Status				
	Employee	0 (0)	1 (1,1)	0,368÷
	Disabled	1 (1,1)	0 (0)	
	Retired	92 (98,9)	92 (98,9)	
Monthly Income				
	<600 Ευρώ	62 (66,7)	65 (70,7)	

≥600 Ευρώ	31 (33,3)	27 (29,3)	0,258÷
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÷Pearson's X² test +Student's t-test

From table 2,, it can be seen that the population the present study, it was found that the mean age of the patients was similar in both groups, for the intervention group it was 79.9 years (SD=8.4) and 78.5 (SD=8.8), respectively, for the control group. The advanced age of the patients, as a finding of the present study, is in agreement with the international literature, as well as with studies from Greece, which report that the largest percentage of individuals with HF is aged >65 (Bui et al., 2011; Kollia, 2014; Klindworth et al., 2015; Stavrianopoulos, 2016; Aggelopoulou et al., 2017; Audi et al., 2017; Baert et al., 2018). The prevalence and incidence of HF, according to the literature, are increasing in developed countries, due to the effectiveness of secondary prevention interventions, the aging of the global population, and the development of advanced therapies that increase the survival rate of patients with cardiovascular diseases (Yancy et al., 2017; Wazqar & Al-Saud, 2023). The chronic syndrome affects approximately 2-5% of adults aged 65-75 years and >10% of adults aged 80 years and older (Klindworth et al., 2015; Audi et al., 2017; Wazqar & Al-Saud, 2023). The most vulnerable population is the elderly. Of the individuals who will need healthcare services due to the presence of symptoms of dyspnea, one in six, according to the ESC, will have undiagnosed HF (Ponikowski et al., 2016).

Regarding gender, the results of the present study found that most participating patients were male, 56% in the intervention group and 53% respectively in the control group. The results are consistent with the findings of similar studies, where men predominated in the chronic syndrome of HF (Kollia, 2014; Yu et al., 2015; Wan et al., 2016; Stavrianopoulos, 2016; Baert et al., 2018). In a cross-sectional population study for the analysis and correlation of gender, sociodemographic factors, lifestyle, health characteristics, with the prevalence of HF, it was found that the factors associated with the prevalence of HF in men, in addition to age, were ischemic heart disease and comorbidities (Cesaroni et al., 2021). CHD is reported as a significant etiological factor in men, relative to women, with an age-adjusted odds ratio. The incidence of CHD increases sharply in peri- and postmenopausal women (Cerber et al., 2015; Chamberlain et al., 2020). Furthermore, it was observed that gender (men, women), represents the behavioral norms applied by the male and female genders, in society, which influence the daily actions, activities, expectations, as well as the experiences of individuals. It was shown that, gender determines the help-seeking behavior, access to healthcare and individual use of the healthcare system (Regitz-Zagrosek., 2020).

The majority of study participants were primary school graduates, married and low-income, with a monthly income of <600 Euros. 67% of the intervention group were married, with this percentage in the control group reaching 56%. The findings of the present study are in agreement with an observational study by Aggelopoulou et al., (2017), as well as with the RCT of Kollia, (2014). Similar are the findings in the cross-sectional study by Seid et al., (2020), in which patients from rural areas were found to have a lower educational level. The level of education and the close relationship with socioeconomic status were predictors of reduced Quality of Life (QoL) and readmissions (Carlson et al., 2013). A possible explanation is that low financial resources, together with the inability to understand medical instructions, result in a lack of adherence to therapeutic pharmaceutical and dietary recommendations and, therefore, reduced effectiveness of disease management. Similar to the results of the study, are those of Noori et al., (2014), where it was shown that illiterate patients are less oriented towards the importance of instructions for taking medications according to the instructions given, as well as adherence to diet and physical activity, exercise, compared to patients with a higher educational level.

From the demographic data of this study, the patient sample was residents of a large agricultural prefecture, with a geographical distribution of many small and remote communities, with a fairly large distance in kilometers from health services, which requires the loss of time, resources and financial cost, making it difficult and often impossible to provide health care support, to cover urgent and individualized health needs for chronic patients with HF, after discharge from the hospital, as was also shown by a similar study by Negarandeh et al., (2019). Most intervention and cardiac rehabilitation programs for patients with HF take place in large urban centers, making it difficult to monitor transitional intervention programs, as well as rehabilitation programs, by patients living in rural, provincial and remote areas (Zhai et al., 2017; Gardiner et al., 2019). The following table presents the demographic data of the patients, by group:

Clinical Characteristics

Table 4. Clinical Characteristics by Group

	Intervention Group, N = 93	Control Group, N = 93	p-value
	N (%)	N (%)	
Basic Etiology of Heart Failure			
Arterial Hypertension	14 (15)	13 (14)	0,999÷
Valvular Disease	14 (15)	16 (17)	0,842÷

Ischemic Cardiomyopathy	3 (3,2)	1 (1,1)	0,613÷
Chronic Atrial Fibrillation	30 (32)	31 (33,6)	0,479÷
Coronary Heart Disease	45 (48)	52 (56)	0,378÷
Congenital Heart Disease	3 (3,2)	1 (1,1)	0,613÷
Other Chronic Diseases -Comorbidities			
Arterial Hypertension	5 (5,4)	7 (7,5)	0,765÷
Chronic Kidney Disease	13 (14)	16 (17)	0,686÷
Pulmonary Hypertension	1 (1,1)	2 (2,2)	0,999÷
Diabetes Mellitus	14 (15)	27 (29)	0,034 ÷
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	17 (18)	9 (9,7)	0,139÷
Other	2 (2,2)	4 (4,3)	0,689÷
Time since first diagnosis of Heart Failure			
1-2 years	5 (5,4)	4 (4,3)	0,987÷
>2 years	88 (95)	89 (96)	
Ejection Fraction			
<40%	49 (52)	52 (56)	0,598÷
≥40%	44 (48)	41 (44)	
Previous Number of Hospital Admissions for Heart Failure			
<1 month	39 (41,9)	52 (55,9)	
1-2 months	52 (55,9)	34 (36,6)	0,057÷
>3 months	2 (2,2)	7 (7,5)	

÷Pearson's X² test

As shown in table 3., from the clinical data of this study, most participating patients had comorbidities, with a higher frequency of Diabetes Mellitus (DM), Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD), Arterial Hypertension and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD). In particular, the comorbidity of DM was found to be significantly different in patients in the control group who more frequently presented the comorbidity, at a rate of 29%, compared to patients in the intervention group (15%). The findings are in line with the international literature, where it was observed that comorbidities are strong predictors of negative outcomes (McMurray et al., 2012; Sousa et al., 2017; Baert et al., 2018). Similar results were found in the study by Audi et al., (2017), with a rate of 42.7% and comorbidities such as diabetes, peripheral vascular disease and cerebrovascular disease, being factors responsible for the reduced performance of daily activities, repeated unplanned readmissions, as well as increasing healthcare costs. Similar results were found in the study by Rahimi et al., (2014), where it was found that, in addition to age, gender and NYHA functional class, renal function, blood pressure, sodium level, EF, natriuretic peptide level, diabetes, BMI and exercise, affect patient outcome. Also, the results of the present study are in agreement with those of Noori et al., (2014), who investigated the effect of socioeconomic status on patient readmissions and it was

shown that EF<40%, poor physical activity, lack of exercise, non-adherence to medication and arterial hypertension are identified as significant independent predictors for repeated unplanned readmissions and rehospitalizations.

Marginally, with a non-significant difference for hospital admissions for HF, it appeared from the clinical characteristics of the patients, at their entry into the present study, that 55.9% (52 patients) of the control group had been admitted to the hospital in less than 1 month for HF and the corresponding percentage in the intervention group was 41.9% (39 patients). In contrast, for the period of 1-2 months, 55.9% (52 patients) of the intervention group had been admitted to the hospital, while the percentage in the control group, for the same period, was 36.6% (34 patients). For the period of more than 3 months, two patients in the intervention group, a percentage (2.2%), had rehospitalization, when the percentage in the control group was 7.5% (7 patients), for the same period. The causes of patient readmissions include clinical characteristics, laboratory findings, biochemical parameters, biomarkers, non-compliance with the HF treatment regimen, advanced age of patients, and comorbidities. From the results of the literature review studies, it has been shown that polypharmacy and low socioeconomic level are associated with readmissions (Gabet et al., 2015; Oyanguren et al., 2016; Dinatolo et al., 2018; Lahoz et al., 2020; de Goes Marques et al., 2022; Browder & Rosamond, 2023).

In the telephone contact with the researcher, up to 6 months, all the patients in the study answered the telephone calls. From 6 months to the 1st year, 22.6% (21 patients) of the intervention group did not respond to the telephone contact and the corresponding percentage in the control group was 19.4% (18 patients). From the review of the literature, it was found that the loss of participants in the RCTs may be due to fatigue, which is caused by the long research period of 12 months. Also, some of the participants may have found it difficult to participate in the individual, personalized telephone interviews and in the telephone monitoring of each research period (Otsu & Moriyama, 2014). Similar findings of participant loss were found in the RCT of Deek, Nouredin, & Davidson, (2020), where 5% of the sample was lost within 30 days of the study. The ACC/AHA guidelines (2013) recommend telephone follow-up within 3 days after patients' discharge from the hospital. In our study, the first telephone contact was made on the 7th day after the patients' discharge and up to the 6th month there was no loss of participants in the researcher's telephone calls during each time period of the study. After the first 6 months of telephone follow-up, this period coincides with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. It is possible that, during this period, patients have changed their place of residence, living with their family, in order to manage the self-care of HF, which is demanding and difficult, due to the conditions and the adoption of emergency measures during the pandemic period, as well as in the case of possible COVID-19 disease, to receive the support of their families. The patients in the study were elderly and a large percentage of the patients did not have a mobile phone, resulting in the researcher not being able to communicate with

this portion of the patients when they changed their residence. From the literature, regarding the factors that may be responsible for the loss of participants from the RCTs, the demographic and clinical characteristics of the sample (socioeconomic and psychological factors), the severity of the disease affecting functional capacity and physical condition, psychological reasons, mental disorders (depression), change of place of residence, as well as the COVID-19 pandemic were found to be related. It was also shown that in chronic patients of low and middle income, the lack of knowledge about the chronic disease, the duration of treatment and non-compliance with it, contributed to the loss of participants from the follow-up of chronic patients in the studies (Tong, Koh, & Lee, 2023). The table below lists the clinical characteristics of the participants by group.

The following table presents the descriptive data for the subfactors and the total scale of perceived SS, by time point and the size of the Cohen's d difference, by group. The subfactor related to Family/SO ranges from 8 to 56 points, while the subfactor Friends, from 4 to 28 points. The total scale ranges from 12 to 84 points, with higher values corresponding to greater perceived SS.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Social Support Scale per Group and Time Period

	Group			Effect Size Cohen's d
	N	Intervention	Control	
Total Social Support		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Discharge	186	68,4 (8,5)	71,5 (7,2)	0,4
1 st Week	166	70,5 (7,3)	69,8 (9,9)	-0,1
1 st Month	162	70,9 (7)	70,2 (8)	-0,1
6 th Month	156	68,3 (8,6)	65,1 (12)	-0,3
1 st Year	67	66,8 (10,9)	66,2 (12,6)	<0,1
Family /Significant Others				
Discharge	186	53,3 (5,7)	54,2 (5,1)	0,2
1 st Week	166	54,4 (4,7)	53,5 (8,5)	-0,1
1 st Month	162	53,8 (4)	53,8 (6,2)	<0,1
6 th Month	156	52,4 (6)	47,7 (8,9)	-0,6
1 st Year	67	50,8 (8,2)	49,9 (9,1)	-0,1
Friends				
Discharge	186	15 (6,6)	17,3 (6,3)	0,3
1 st Week	166	16,1 (5,6)	16,3 (7,3)	<0,1
1 st Month	162	17,1 (5,3)	16,4 (7)	-0,1
6 th Month	156	15,9 (6,6)	17,5 (7,4)	0,2
1 st Year	67	16 (7,5)	16,4 (8,6)	<0,1

As can be seen from the table 4. above, at discharge, there is a moderate difference between the 2 groups, intervention and control, in terms of overall perceived SS (Cohen's $d=0.4$), with the intervention group having a lower score, therefore less perceived SS, compared to the control group. This difference decreases in the remaining time periods, there is no significant difference between the two groups of the study. A similar picture is presented in the subfactor concerning support from Friends, while for Family/SO the difference is moderate to high only at 6 months, where the intervention group has a higher score, therefore higher perceived support from Family/SO, compared to the control group.

Table 6., then presents descriptive data for the dimensions and the total self-care scale, by time point, and the Cohen's d difference size, per group. The subfactors related to application, fluid management, and physical self-care range from 3 to 15 points and the total scale from 9 to 45 points, with lower values indicating better self-care.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Self-Care Scale per Group and Time Point

	N	Group		Effect Size Cohen's d
		Intervention	Control	
Total Self-Care		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Discharge	186	30,7 (7,2)	31,1 (6,9)	0,1
1 st Week	166	24,5 (6,9)	30,6 (7,8)	0,8
1 st Month	162	22,9 (6,1)	28,8 (6,8)	0,9
6 th Month	156	25,1 (7,8)	31,4 (8,3)	0,8
1 st Year	67	24,5 (6,2)	25,4 (7,9)	0,1
Implementation of instructions				
Discharge	186	9,1 (2,4)	9 (2,4)	<0,1
1 st Week	166	7,2 (2,3)	9,2 (2,8)	0,8
1 st Month	162	6,6 (2)	8,6 (2,5)	0,9
6 th Month	156	7,8 (2,5)	10,3 (2,8)	>0,9
1 st Year	67	7,2 (1,9)	7,9 (2,5)	0,3
Fluid Management				
Discharge	186	10,5 (3)	10,9 (2,8)	0,1
1 st Week	166	8 (2,5)	10,5 (3)	0,9
1 st Month	162	7,2 (2,2)	9,7 (2,5)	1,1

6 th Month	156	8,2 (2,7)	10,4 (2,7)	0,8
1 st Year	67	8,4 (2,4)	8,7 (3,1)	0,1
Physical Self-Care				
Discharge	186	11,2 (2,7)	11,2 (2,6)	<0,1
1 st Week	166	9,3 (2,6)	10,9 (2,7)	0,6
1 st Month	162	9,1 (2,5)	10,4 (2,4)	0,5
6 th Month	156	9,1 (3)	10,6 (2,8)	0,5
1 st Year	67	8,9 (2,5)	8,8 (2,8)	<0,1

At discharge, regarding the total self-care scale, there is a minimal difference between the intervention group and the control group (Cohen's $d=0.1$), while during the study, this difference increases, where in the 1st Week, the intervention group presents a lower mean score, a better level of self-care, compared to the control group, with a large difference size (Cohen's $d=0.8$), which is maintained in the 1st month and at six months ($d=0.9$ and $d=0.8$, respectively). In the 1st year, there is a minimal difference size in both groups ($d=0.1$). The same happens for the individual dimensions of the self-care scale.

To change the patients' scores on the self-care scale, over the follow-up time and to control for the interaction of time and intervention, Linear Mixed Models were used and the results are given in the tables (7,8,9, 10) that follow.

Table 7. Mixed Linear Model for the Effect of Intervention on Total Self-Care

Factor	B+	95% Δ.E+++	p-value
Intervention (Yes vs No)	-2,9	-4,9, -0,89	0,707
Time Period	-0,44	-0,87, -0,01	0,046
Intervention * Time Period	-0,85	-1,4, -0,26	0,005

+ Dependency ratio + dependency ratio ++95% Confidence interval

Table 8. Mixed Linear Model for the Effect of Intervention on Implementation (Self-Care)

Factor	B+	95% Δ.E++	p-value
Intervention (Yes vs No)	-0,78	-1,5, -0,11	0,903
Time Period	0,11	-0,05, 0,27	0,196
Intervention * Time Period	-0,44	-0,65, -0,22	<0,001

+ Dependency ratio + dependency ratio ++95% Confidence interval

Table 9. Mixed Linear Model for the Effect of Intervention on Fluid Management (Self-Care)

Factor	B+	95% Δ.E++	p-value
Intervention (Yes vs No)	-1,4	-2,1, -0,66	0,325
Time Period	-0,26	-0,42, -0,09	0,003
Intervention * Time Period	-0,24	-0,47, -0,01	0,038

+ Dependency ratio + dependency ratio ++95% Confidence interval

Table 10. Mixed Linear Model for the Effect of Intervention on Physical Self-Care

Factor	B+	95% Δ.E++	p-value
Intervention (Yes vs No)	-0,70	-1,4, 0,03	0,060
Time Period	-0,30	-0,45, -0,15	<0,001
Intervention * Time Period	-0,17	-0,38, 0,03	<0,001

+ Dependency ratio + dependency ratio ++95% Confidence interval

Pearson correlation coefficients for the Self-Care Behavior and SS scales

Next, Pearson's correlation coefficients for the Self-Care and SS scales are presented.

		Total Social Support (MSPSS)
Total Self-Care (Gr9- EHFScBS)	r	-0,38
	P	<0,001

Discussion

In the present study, from the statistical analysis, a significant negative correlation was found between the perceived SS scale and the Self-Care behavior scale ($p < 0.001$). The increase in the total perceived SS was associated with better overall Self-Care behavior. It was also observed, from the statistical analysis, for the study of demographic and clinical characteristics and their possible correlation with the level of total Self-Care behavior that the perceived SS from the Family/SO was statistically significantly correlated ($p = 0.002$) with the level of Self-Care behavior of the patients in the study. This finding is likely due to the fact that the chronic patients in the study, with the perceived SS from the Family/SO, felt comfortable, confident, and self-assured in managing, maintaining, and engaging with the complex nature of the chronic HF syndrome. The above findings are in agreement with the international literature,

which demonstrates that increasing perceived SS from the Family/SO contributes to improving Self-Care behavior and self-efficacy (Hammash et al., 2017; Uchmanowicz et al., 2017; Cavalcante et al., 2018). High perceived SS, which comes from the Family/SO, can enhance and facilitate patients' self-confidence, empowerment, in relation to their abilities for self-control, self-service, as well as for self-efficacy and optimal Self-Care behaviors (Graven & Grant, 2014; Beckie et al., 2017; Chamberlain, 2017). The level of Self-Care behavior of patients with HF can be positively influenced by the higher level of perceived SS, which in turn positively influences Self-Care confidence, as well as self-maintenance, self-management of Self-Care behaviors (Chen et al., 2017; Hammash et al., 2017; Fivecoat, Sayers, & Riegel, 2018; Graven et al., 2019). Also, the results of the present study are in agreement with the findings of the study by Shahriari et al., (2016), in which it was observed that increased support from the Family had a positive outcome of self-confidence, self-efficacy and, consequently, improvement in Self-Care behavior of patients with HF, due to high perceived SS. Similar results were found in the study by Chamberlain, (2017), attempting in his comparative descriptive study to evaluate the characteristics of perceived SS and Self-Care behavior of patients with HF, who had been hospitalized with HF dysregulation.

The population of the present study, from their demographic data, consisted of elderly patients, who resided in the region, in a mostly agricultural county, consisting of many small, geographically remote villages from the capital of the county and in which population, the family still maintained its cohesion. In their majority, the patients were married, lived with their partner and received enough SS, suggesting the presence of enhanced family support. From studies, living with a partner and family, was found to be associated with greater self-confidence Self-care and self-management of the chronic syndrome of HF (Hammash et al., 2017; Uchmanowicz et al., 2017; Cavalcante et al., 2018). Also, the results of our study are in agreement with those of Khaledi et al., (2014), in which it was observed that higher perceived SS led to improved Self-Care behavior. It was found that the higher average level of support from Family/SO, represented the strongest correlation with Self-Care behavior. The chronic patients of the present study, who did not have a partner and lived alone, the existence of informal support networks, which in the context of the Greek family is increased, received support, as usually happens in small societies, remote regional communities, possibly from neighbors and close or distant relatives. The above findings are likely due to the fact that Family Support is considered one of the most important components of perceived SS, especially for chronic patients and plays the vital role of support, assistance, home care and management of the chronic syndrome. According to the literature, high perceived SS and enhanced self-confidence of chronic patients influence the maintenance of therapeutic regimens, dietary instructions, as well as their participation in decision-making related to symptom management and the desired treatment (Sayers et al., 2008; Riegel et al., 2009; Gallagher et al., 2011; Graven

& Grant, 2014). Furthermore, an old research study found that in chronic patients aged >65 years, increased perceived social support from their spouses/partners contributes to a reduced risk of functional decline and improvement in their daily life. Also, in elderly chronic patients with comorbidities, the presence of a wider social network was found to be strongly associated with a lower risk of functional decline (Bisschop et al., 2003).

In our study, the perceived SS from the Family/SO sub factor, upon the introduction of the patients into the study, was similarly increased in both groups, and was maintained similarly until the 1st month. However, at 6 months, a large difference was observed between the two groups, with the intervention group receiving the highest perceived support from Family/SO, which was not maintained until 12 months, but both groups of the study continued to receive a high score.

It should be mentioned that in our study, the time period after the first six months of telephone follow-up coincides with the spread of the coronavirus and the COVID-19 pandemic, resulting in the imposition of all mandatory distancing measures, refraining from unnecessary outings and maintaining social distancing, to reduce the spread and spread of the virus. In our study, patients with HF, with the imposition of mandatory COVID-19 containment measures, lived alone or married with their spouse/partner and received support from informal SS networks, Friends/neighbors/distant relatives, small communities, remote communities in the region. The new lifestyle approaches had affected people in general, but even more so the chronically ill, physically, psychologically and socially. In the study by Li et al., (2021), which was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, it was found that high perceived informal SS was associated with appropriate Self-Care behavior and better outcome of chronic disease of HF. It was also found to protect the mental health of chronic patients from the negative outcomes of social vulnerability and social isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic. A study in community-dwelling elderly people reported that reduced social participation due to COVID-19 was associated with reduced physical activity and the occurrence of depressive symptoms (Yamada et al., 2021). According to the researchers, HF patients are likely to have physical, social vulnerability, cognitive impairment, depressive symptoms, and the overlap of these conditions leads to adverse events. Accordingly, in the study by Shakata et al., (2023), it was found that social distancing, restriction of going out and social participation of elderly chronic patients with HF, restriction of family visits, and social isolation were associated with the development of social weakness and depression in chronic patients.

Conclusions

The findings of this study revealed that the effect of the dual nursing intervention on the Self-Care behavior of patients with HF was found to be enhanced by the nursing educational approach, nursing follow-up, and perceived support, empowerment, and increased awareness

of patients, leading to better management of the chronic and clinically evolving syndrome. The findings of the study highlight the importance of designing effective non-pharmacological management programs, continuous contact, communication, support, follow-up, and increased social network. Interventions that include SS, for the patients themselves, their families/caregivers, strengthening the Self-Care behavior of patients with HF, are deemed necessary.

Limitations of the Study

The most important limitation of the study is the fact that during its duration, a large percentage of the sample was lost, either because it was not possible to contact them, or because of death, resulting in not much information about the course of the patients and their overall outcome.

Another limitation is that the study was single-center, involving a Secondary General Hospital, in a rural Prefecture, based on the agricultural and livestock population. A multicenter study or a study in which an urban population would also participate, might have provided a more representative sample, with a greater possibility of generalizing the findings.

Also, a limitation of the study is the questionnaire responses, possibly because the patients were not honest or because they did not want to create a bad image for the researcher during the interview or because the patients had difficulty understanding the questions, due to their low educational level and lack of familiarity with the research process, as well as their possible clinical condition, which did not allow them to answer the questions of the tools correctly. Even the long duration of patient follow-up may have created fatigue in the patients.

The dual educational nursing approach strategy, which consisted of special education and discharge guidance for patients with HF from the hospital and telephone follow-up, proved effective, in relation to the results evaluated in the study, but their correlation does not allow the evaluation of the effectiveness of each individual strategy, creating the need for studies on these strategies, individually and with an increased follow-up time.

Another limiting parameter was that the research coincided with the time period of the Covid-19 pandemic, with the special conditions, where care for the patients was likely to be provided by the family itself or by new caregivers. As a result of these new conditions, after 6 months, it appeared that the cycle of follow-up and recording of a

large percentage of the sample was lost. Therefore, the final sample of the research was small for valid conclusions to be drawn, while if all the patient data had been available in total, it would have likely modified the final result of the study.

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